

Spoke 6

Deliverable n. 10

Technical-scientific report of the results achieved in concrete application scenarios

Final Report on results and results' effectiveness

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1. Deliverable Information

Deliverable 10 marks the completion of the activities carried out under WPs 3, 4 and 5, dedicated respectively to Restoration, Monitoring and Sharing. These WPs have formed the core of Spoke 6's activities following the preparatory phase (WP1) and the preliminary surveys (WP2). Restoration activities encompass all fieldwork, including excavation, restoration design and the application of restoration products, whilst monitoring includes measures aimed at managing materials and monuments and assessing the state of deterioration before, during and after restoration work. Finally, dissemination activities encompass not only the actual sharing of information but also the development of wide-ranging strategies for preventive conservation through the involvement of the public, institutions and private enterprises.

***Indicators:** Typological variability and representativeness of the contexts examined in relation to the risk scenarios. Representativeness of the conservation approach and restoration interventions in relation to the methodologies, materials, guidelines defined in the design context.*

1.1 Deliverable History

Writing of Deliverable 10 was due by November 2025, previous end date of the project. Due to successive delays (first to February 2026, then to April), Deliverable 10 has continued to be implemented according to the new data, and the possibility to better investigate the impact of undertaken actions. It has been therefore completed by April 30th, 2026.

2. Spoke Information

The aim of the Spoke 6 within the CHANGES Project is to develop and apply integrated methodologies, strategies and approaches to support the processes of historical understanding, conservation, restoration, monitoring, sustainable and participatory planning in multi-layered contexts of CH. The proposed approach will integrate humanistic, historical-archaeological, art-historical, scientific and technological research aimed at the acquisition, management and analysis of complex data, necessary to produce theoretical and practical-operational knowledge. The proposed method will also improve the citizens' lives, thanks to the promotion of cultural participation as a factor of social cohesion and sustainability.

These objectives will be pursued through the active involvement of the population in the various project phases to raise awareness of issues concerning CH, such as the need for safeguarding and conservation as participation, where the act of restoration is shared and explained in the methodological and critical choices in order to recognize the common CH, both socially and historically.

Cities with a long and continuous history and landscapes share problems of coexistence with the relics of the past, even in the form of ruins, and face the challenges imposed by the pushes for change in contemporary society and ongoing climate change. Museums, archives, art galleries, parks and archaeological areas, historic centres, landscape and underwater contexts constitute

ideal venues for setting up a system of shared strategies and approaches, within which the multidisciplinary team that forms the spoke moves.

It is also necessary to address the continuous needs of preventive and scheduled monitoring and maintenance, as well as the respectful conservation and restoration of historical values and meanings and, above all, of the inalienable drive to enhancement and the right of communities to use it (as well as the restoration of historical buildings with the contributions of humanistic historical/archaeological, geoarchaeological and archaeometric research for their ability to reconstruct contexts through the testimonies of “material” and “immaterial”, architectural-engineering culture). Furthermore, it is indispensable to decipher the economic and legal dimensions for the study of shared fruition models in conjunction with a scientific-technological analysis of their material supports and the interactions between these and the external environment.

2.1 Spoke Partners

Spoke’s team includes Universities (UniCT, UniBO, UniTO, UniMI, UniSOB, UniNA), public institutions (ICR, OPD) and one private foundation (F1563), representatives therefore of different approaches to cultural heritage. Involved specialists include archaeologists, art historians, architects, engineers, physicists, chemists and geologists, as well as computer scientists, conservators and restorers, allowing therefore a global approach to material objects and sites.

Partners
Leader P1 Università degli Studi di Catania – UniCT
Co-leader P2 Istituto Centrale del Restauro – ICR
P3 Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
P4 Fondazione 1563 (F1563)
P5 Opificio Pietro Dure (OPD)
P6 Università degli Studi di Milano (UniMI)
P7 Università degli Studi di Torino (UniTO)
P8 Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa (UniSOB)
P9 Università Federico II di Napoli (UniNA)

3. Technical–Scientific Report of the Results Achieved in Concrete Application Scenarios

Deliverable 10 marks the conclusion of the activities carried out within WPs 3, 4, and 5, respectively dedicated to Restoration, Monitoring, and Sharing. These WPs represented the core of the activities of Spoke 6 following the preparation phase (WP1) and the preliminary investigations (WP2).

Restoration activities include all on-site interventions, such as excavation, restoration design, and the application of restoration products. Monitoring activities, on the other hand, encompass interventions aimed at managing materials and monuments, as well as assessing the state of deterioration both before, during, and after restoration work. Finally, sharing activities include not only dissemination itself, but also the development of broad strategies for preventive conservation through the involvement of the public, institutions, and private enterprises.

Indicators: Typological variability and representativeness of the contexts examined in relation to the risk scenarios. Representativeness of the conservation approach and restoration interventions in relation to the methodologies, materials, guidelines defined in the design context.

4. Executive Summary

This technical–scientific report summarizes the results achieved by Spoke 6 (History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage) within the CHANGES Project – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next Generation EU, funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR).

4.1 General Framework and Project Objectives

The CHANGES Project – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next Generation EU, developed within the Extended Partnerships funded by the PNRR, had as its main objective the strengthening of the interaction between the humanities and the hard sciences, with particular reference to the Cultural Heritage sector.

Within this framework operates Spoke 6 – History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage, coordinated by the University of Catania. The objective of Spoke 6 was the development of integrated methodologies for:

- the historical understanding of cultural heritage (WP2–3)
- conservation and restoration (WP3)
- the management and monitoring of cultural assets (WP4–5)

At the same time, the project aimed to strengthen the relationship between research, society, and the production system, through the involvement of public bodies (archaeological parks, heritage authorities, museums, local administrations), collaboration with companies through cascade funding calls, and an extensive dissemination activity.

To address the complexity of these objectives, activities were structured according to a multi-scalar approach, involving the selection of case studies representative of the full range of tangible cultural heritage, from individual artifacts to landscapes:

- micro-scale (artifacts and collections)
- meso-scale (monuments and sites)
- macro-scale (cities and territory).

At the same time, case studies were further articulated based on chronology (from the Upper Palaeolithic to the 1980s), typology (artifacts, ecofacts, historical-artistic objects, archaeological finds), and context (confined, semi-confined, or open; urban and extra-urban, with peri-urban referring to monuments within archaeological parks connected to urban centers). The common thread among these case studies is the concept of the stratified landscape, a defining feature of Italian cultural heritage, where different historical layers often overlap, even within a single artifact. Additional variables such as typology, chronology, and location were also considered across the different scales. As a result, archaeological, historical-artistic, and architectural contexts were selected to represent diverse conditions in terms of risk, intervention methods, and enhancement strategies, often working with contrasting pairs. These include cultural assets in urban areas — subject to specific degradation factors — and those in extra-urban settings, as well as monuments in outdoor and indoor contexts, and confined or semi-confined artifacts.

The materials studied cover the entire spectrum of tangible cultural heritage, from archaeological finds to architectural monuments, from bioarchaeological remains to artistic objects, across a chronological span from the Palaeolithic to the present day. The scale of investigation also varies, ranging from interventions on individual artifacts or masonry to topographic-scale projects (archaeological or architectural complexes) and territorial-scale initiatives.

This structured approach enabled the development and testing of integrated methodologies across diverse contexts, ensuring both replicability and transferability of results.

4.2 Micro-scale Interventions: Artifacts, Innovative Materials, and Collections

Micro-scale activities focused on material studies, diagnostics, and collection management, with a strong emphasis on advanced analytical methodologies and data structuring.

These interventions represent the frontier of technological innovation applied to the conservation of movable heritage and architectural finishes, involving a synergistic collaboration between the University of Catania (UniCT), the Central Institute for Restoration (ICR), the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD), the University of Milan (UniMI), and the University of Bologna (UniBO).

4.2.1 Artifacts and Innovative Materials

I. Geopolymers and the Monastery of the Benedictines in Catania (UniCT)

A key pillar of this intervention scale is the research conducted by the DSBGA departments of UniCT at the Monastery of the Benedictines of San Nicolò l’Arena in Catania¹. The study focused on the development of alkali-activated materials (geopolymers), formulated according to the

¹ For bibliographical references regarding the research carried out at the Benedictine Monastery (CT), see M. Fugazzotto et al. (eds.), *Catania. The CHANGES Project and the Benedictine Monastery*, Edizioni Quasar, Rome 2025, with the bibliography cited therein.

European DNSH (Do No Significant Harm) principle, aimed at replacing traditional products with eco-sustainable “zero-kilometer” solutions. Aluminosilicate powders such as metakaolin, Sicilian diatomite, fly ash, and industrial ceramic waste were used as precursors. The experimentation led to the creation of repair mortars, plasters, and injectable consolidants, tested in pilot sites such as the East Cloister (for the replication of degraded majolica), the halls of the ancient Refectory, and the Roman Domus (for the reproduction of black-and-white mosaic tesserae).

Technical results, validated through pXRF, DRIFT, SEM-EDS analyses and pull-off tests, demonstrate high mineralogical compatibility and mechanical strength.

For public engagement, virtual tours using Matterport technology were developed by the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science (DMI), allowing users to visualize restoration outcomes before and after intervention².

Experimental interventions along the same lines were also conducted in the Cathedral of Cefalù.

II. Volatile Binding Media and the Santo Chiodo Warehouse in Spoleto (OPD)

In parallel, the OPD coordinated cutting-edge research on Volatile Binding Media (VBM), aimed at identifying sustainable and reversible alternatives to cyclododecane for securing artworks in emergency contexts³. These include wooden and stone sculptures and other materials recovered from churches and monuments damaged by the 2011 earthquake in central Italy, currently housed in the purpose-built Santo Chiodo storage facility in Spoleto.

The study analysed compounds such as menthol and menthyl lactate, evaluating their sublimation kinetics and the absence of organic residues through FT-IR spectroscopy. A significant operational success was the transport of the Crucifix by Giovanni Teutonico (1494) from Norcia. The artwork, which had remained under rubble for 15 months and exposed to freeze-thaw cycles, showed extreme decohesion, with over 1.4 kg of debris accumulated in the torso. The use of molten menthyl lactate (approximately 3 kg applied to the entire sculpture), injected beneath the paint layers, allowed temporary stabilization without irreversible adhesives, ensuring ten times greater cohesion than menthol during handling. Transport was carried out in a double shock-absorbing crate equipped with 3D-printed supports (stereolithographic resin masks), designed using digital models of the artwork.

III. Mural Painting: Hypogea and New Muralism (ICR)

At the same time, the ICR chose to operate on mural paintings preserved in two different types of contexts—hypogean and open-air—each requiring distinct intervention approaches.

² Barbagallo S.P., Fugazzotto M., Longhitano L., Occhipinti R., Allegra D., Barone G., Mazzoleni P., Stanco F., Hidden monuments revealed: 3D digitization of the Benedictine Monastery of Catania and its stratified spaces, in Proceedings of IMEKO TC26 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage.

³ A. Acciai et al., *Applicazione dei leganti volatili nei contesti emergenziali*, in F. Bocasso et. al. (a cura di), *Progetti e ricerche per la conservazione del patrimonio culturale*, Edizioni Quasar, Roma 2025, pp. 37–62.

In hypogean contexts, the ICR worked on the Crypt of Saints Peter and Paul in Matera⁴, validating the effectiveness of nanolime in aqueous dispersion (Nanolaq) for the consolidation of wall paintings in environments with near-saturation humidity levels (96–99%). The research led to the development of a data-driven preventive conservation model, where monitoring CO₂ peaks (rising from 460 to over 1300 ppm in the presence of operators) made it possible to define controlled working shifts (1 hour of activity followed by 2 hours of pause) to prevent calcium carbonate solubilization.

For brown alterations caused by manganese oxides, a combined strategy was developed involving laser photoablation and chemical transformation through redox reactions (hydroxylammonium chloride and hydrazine in hydrogel).

Similar investigative activities were carried out in Matera at the churches of San Francesco d’Assisi and on the painting of the *Last Supper* in the former refectory of the Conservatory of San Giuseppe. Comparable pilot projects were also conducted in Ausonia (FR), in the crypt of the Sanctuary of Santa Maria del Piano, and in Positano, in the triclinium of the hypogean villa of MAR. In open-air contexts, another field of excellence concerns the conservation of Contemporary New Muralism⁵, exemplified by the intervention on the mural “*Nido di Vespe*” by Lucamaleonte in Rome. The ICR tested eco-sustainable hydrogels (PVA-borax) for selective cleaning and developed fluorescent fillers enhanced with zinc oxide (ZnO) as UV markers, ensuring the recognizability of the intervention under Wood’s light.

IV. Black Crusts Analysis (UniMI)

In the field of environmental diagnostics, the University of Milan analysed the impact of pollutants on black crusts at the Monumental Cemetery of Milan⁶ using LIBS and Raman techniques. The aim was to characterize the chemical and mineralogical composition of the crusts and to understand the correlation between urban atmospheric pollutants and stone degradation through a multi-analytical approach.

The research combined Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) and Raman spectroscopy, enabling rapid acquisition of both elemental and molecular information and mapping the distribution of heavy metals and carbonaceous particulate within the gypsum matrix of the crust.

⁴ S. Iafrate et al., *Il progetto di restauro e fruizione della “Cripta” dei Santi Pietro e Paolo*, in F. Bocasso (a cura di), *Progetti e ricerche per la conservazione del patrimonio culturale*, Edizioni Quasar, Roma 2025, pp. 11–24 with the bibliography cited therein.

⁵ P. Mezzadri et al., *La conservazione della Street Art e dell’Urban Art*, in F. Bocasso (a cura di), *Progetti e ricerche per la conservazione del patrimonio culturale*, Edizioni Quasar, Roma 2025, pp. 25–36 with the bibliography.

⁶ Bergomi, A.; Comite, V.; Borelli, M.; Lombardi, C.A.; Festa, E.; Oujja, M.; Castillejo, M.; Maestro-Guijarro, L.; Carmona-Quiroga, P.M.; Crespo, A.; et al., Integrated Comprehensive Characterization of Black Crusts from Milan’s Monumental Cemetery: A Synergistic Approach Combining Conventional and Unconventional Analytical Techniques. *Heritage* 2025, 8, 506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage8120506>.

Collaboration with Istemi srl, within the framework of cascade funding calls, enabled high-resolution digitization of ceramic artifacts from the submerged site of Aenaria in Ischia⁷, curated by the University of Milan. Also in Ischia, in collaboration with ARTES Soc. Coop, maintenance and restoration of ceramic finds were carried out in Lacco Ameno. In partnership with Advice SRL, a GIS system was developed for the production, management, analysis, and dissemination of scientific data within the project *“Archaeology and Environment of the “Islands of History” of the Tyrrhenian Sea: The Case of Ischia. Multidisciplinary research into the reconstruction of Mediterranean resources and networks over the centuries”*.

Further archaeometric analyses were conducted – again through Advice SRL – on artifacts from Ischia, Pantalica, Calaforno, and Calicantone, which are among the project’s investigation areas.

4.2.2 Collections

Micro-scale interventions within the CHANGES Project (Spoke 6) also included the enhancement of collections, addressing the challenge of conserving and managing “invisible heritage,” namely the vast body of artifacts and archival materials often confined to storage and inaccessible to the public.

The case studies were:

I. Phaistos- Stratigraphical Museum (UniCT)

The reorganization of the Stratigraphical Museum of Phaistos (Crete), carried out by UniCT (Militello, Toscano, Fadelli, Messina) in collaboration with the Italian Archaeological School of Athens (SAIA), involved the transfer and cleaning of approximately 4,800 crates of materials (excavations from 1900 to 2023). Old wooden boxes were replaced with fireproof polypropylene systems and mobile compact shelving, increasing storage capacity by 30%.

During the transfer, the recovery of legacy data allowed artifacts to be reconnected to their original stratigraphic contexts, digitizing information often preserved on degraded paper labels or even repurposed cigarette packs.

To ensure data interoperability and address gaps in national regulations, new cataloguing tools were developed within the PyArchInIt plugin for QGIS. The Digital Integration module (TMA), developed with Spoke 8 (F. Buscemi), allows:

- standardized cataloguing through controlled vocabularies (avoiding ad hoc linguistic variations)
- linking materials to stratigraphic contexts for spatial and statistical analysis
- optimizing storage management via barcodes and QR codes for the rapid retrieval of records.

The TMA methodology has been successfully applied to the reorganisation of the Stratigraphic Museum of Phaistos, enabling the recovery of legacy data and the reconnection of materials – which were often out of context – to their original stratigraphic units.

⁷ G. Olcese (a cura di), *Ischia. Ricerche nell’ambito del PNRR*, Edizioni Quasar, Roma 2025.

- The “FR” (Faunal Remains) form, devised by Erica Platania, for documenting animal skeletal remains directly in the field, whilst preserving their contextual relationship.
- The “Cardillac” GIS system, designed by Davide-Giulio Aquini for the document management and study of Minoan jewellery, capable of transforming fragmentary data into a searchable, integrated resource.

II. Bologna: The University Osteological Collection (UniBO)

The digitization of the human osteological collection at the University of Bologna (Maria Giovanna Belcastro e Rita Sorrentino), initiated a project aimed at creating a digital platform for the study of skeletal vulnerability, overcoming the physical fragility of remains and enabling advanced morphometric analyses through “digital twins”.

III. Catania: The Institute of Archaeology Collection

The recovery and study of the Photographic Archive of the former Institute of Archaeology of Catania (UniCT, Militello, Fragalà, Toscano) involved approximately 3,000 glass plates (positives and negatives), printing matrices, and thousands of slides. This material reconstructs a century of archaeological research history in Catania and now constitutes an essential visual database for understanding perceptions of antiquity and documenting sites and artifacts prior to modern transformations.

IV. Centuripe. Epigraphic collection

The research on Centuripe and its inscriptions was coordinated by Licandro and Prado. It included the analysis and digital enhancement of the inscriptions of Centuripe preserved at the Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi and other museums in Sicily. The 3D acquisitions were completed in collaboration with the Università degli Studi di Catania, with the aim of making the materials accessible online and within the permanent exhibition “Centuripe Epigrafica” at the Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe.

V. Sanremo: The Grotta dell’Arma Neanderthal Hearths

The digitization of Neanderthal hearths from the Grotta dell’Arma Bussana (Sanremo), carried out by the University of Milan, represents another key case study.

Overall, the micro-scale level served to consolidate foundational methodologies, essential for applications at higher scales.

4.3 Meso-scale Interventions: Monuments and Archaeological Sites

The intermediate scale involved the application of integrated methodologies for the study and restoration of individual monumental complexes, with the active participation of the Universities

of Catania (UniCT), Naples Federico II (UniNA), Suor Orsola Benincasa (UniSOB), Turin (UniTO), and Milan (UniMI).

An ideal setting for experimenting with multidisciplinary approaches, with activities focusing primarily on the Domus of Ariadne and the Casa della Caccia Antica, located in Regio VII, Insula 4.

I. Pompei: The Domus of Ariadne – Knowledge, Restoration, and Inclusive Access (peri-urban context)

The Domus of Ariadne (also known as the House of the Coloured Capitals) is one of the largest residential complexes in Pompeii, covering approximately 1,850 m² across the full depth of an insula. Its complex stratigraphy reflects centuries of transformation, culminating in a layout organized around a Tuscan atrium and two peristyles (one Ionic and one Doric).

The research unit from the University of Naples Federico II (Picone, Mangone, Romano, Morra) applied the “active knowledge” model, integrating historical-critical analysis with advanced geometric surveys and diagnostic monitoring. Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) identified subsurface anomalies linked to buried structures and water management systems, as well as internal discontinuities in columns, interpreted as original wooden cores.

All data were integrated into an HBIM (Heritage Building Information Modeling) system, used as a 3D archive to monitor degradation and plan maintenance. As regards the materials, spectroscopic analyses (XRF, Raman) carried out on the frescoed surfaces of Room 6 and the Blue Exedra have revealed a palette of the highest quality, with extensive use of cinnabar and Egyptian blue. The analyses also highlighted issues relating to 20th-century restoration work, such as the use of cement, which today causes salt efflorescence that is harmful to the pigments. As for the floors, the domus features exquisite opus tessellatum mosaics (notably the panel depicting marine figures in Room 25), which are threatened by rising damp and invasive vegetation. The enhancement strategy involves reopening the site via an inclusive visitor route, using removable walkways and ramps to protect the mosaics from foot traffic and ensure universal accessibility. Overall, this project has resulted in 27 scientific publications and a documentary film.

An important outcome of the work carried out at Domus di Arianna has been the development of a material for use in restoration, based on the study of an ancient tradition: “battuto di lapillo”, a technique used to construct domed roofs and waterproof terraces. It consists of a mixture of volcanic lapilli and lime, applied to vaults and vigorously compacted (battuto) with wooden tools until a solid, lightweight and waterproof surface is formed. Research into “battuto di lapillo” reached an advanced stage through the mechanical characterisation of historical samples, the design and prototyping of new compatible mixes, and collaboration with MAPEI SpA laboratories. The UniNA team studied traditional recipes, analysed historical samples through petrographic and chemical-physical tests, compared analogous Mediterranean techniques, and tested aggregates and specimens supplied by MAPEI SpA. MAPEI SpA was involved through technical

meetings, joint testing plans, laboratory activities, refinement of mix designs, and discussion of future commercialisation pathways for the “battuto di lapillo” prototype. The UniNA group finalised and delivered the restoration guidelines for the Domus of Ariadne to the Archaeological Park of Pompeii, providing technical support for the ongoing detailed design phase and for future conservation work at the site.

The research on “battuto di lapillo” supported the circular-economy approach by transforming historical knowledge into the basis for an innovative restoration product. This process helped define compatible mix designs inspired by a traditional material and opened the way to prototype development, technology transfer, and possible future commercialisation, thus promoting the reuse and valorisation of waste and by-products in conservation practice.

At the same time, the results were sufficiently mature to ensure continuation beyond CHANGES, with a shared university-company roadmap and a first public dissemination event already scheduled in Naples on 28 May 2026.

In parallel, research on “battuto di lapillo” combined historical investigation, laboratory testing, prototype development, and industrial collaboration. This work created a network involving the University of Naples Federico II, the Archaeological Park of Pompeii, MAPEI S.p.A., laboratories, and skilled craftsmen; strengthened technical and scientific competences; and opened concrete prospects for innovation, future commercialisation, and continued collaboration beyond the project.

II. Pompei: The Domus of Old Hunting: Prevention of Biodeterioration (UniTO) (peri-urban area)

The conservation project at the Domus of Old Hunting in Pompeii (Regio VII, Insula 4), led by the University of Turin (UniTO) (Favero Longo, Elia Lo Giudice), represents an advanced model of preventive conservation applied to archaeological buildings in outdoor settings.

Situated adjacent to the vast Domus of Ariadne, this residence was chosen as the site for a systematic approach to tackling the problem of biological deterioration, one of the most persistent and aggressive factors causing degradation in exposed masonry. The research focused on the integrated environmental monitoring of the masonry structures to understand the mechanisms of interaction between the environment and building materials, such as tuff and ancient plaster.

The methodological core of the project lies in studying the correlation between microclimatic parameters – such as relative humidity levels, temperature fluctuations and solar radiation – and the growth rate of biological films, algal biofilms and cyanobacterial colonies. Through this data analysis, the UniTO team aimed to define the bioreceptivity of the materials, that is, their natural predisposition to be colonised by microorganisms depending on the specific environmental conditions of each façade.

The ultimate objective of this monitoring is not merely diagnostic but operational: the project aims to implement data-driven preventive maintenance protocols.

This approach makes it possible to move beyond the traditional “emergency” response, which often requires the use of aggressive chemical biocides that can potentially damage the original material, in favour of “green” and sustainable strategies that slow down the formation of patinas by addressing the underlying environmental causes.

Together with the research conducted in Turin on the King’s Apartment, the experience in Pompeii confirms Spoke 6’s ability to integrate chemical, physical and biological expertise for the preservation of heritage at risk, setting new standards for the protection of decorated surfaces and architectural elevations.

III. Baia Thermal Baths Archaeological Park (suburban area)

The Archaeological Park of the Baia Thermal Baths represents one of the most complex and innovative operational settings of the project, coordinated by the research team from the Suor Orsola Benincasa University (UniSOB) (Rossi, Cennamo, Nicolais, Genovese). Situated in an area shaped by the geological phenomenon of bradyseism, the site is a veritable palimpsest in which ancient history, natural transformations and contemporary anthropogenic pressures intertwine seamlessly. The research has focused in particular on the Mercurio Sector, using Environment F as a construction site-laboratory to test a multidisciplinary model of conservation and enhancement for outdoor archaeological sites.

The main conservation challenge at Baia is the synergistic interaction between high relative humidity, environmental salinity and biodeterioration. To tackle this “invisible enemy”, the research team adopted a cutting-edge diagnostic approach based on metagenomics. Using DNA metabarcoding techniques (sequencing of the 16S and 18S genes), it was possible to map with extreme precision the microbial communities – such as filamentous cyanobacteria of the genus *Nodularia* and the green microalgae *Picocystis salinarum* – that colonise the mosaics and plasterwork, adapting to extreme conditions of salinity and low light.

In the field of restoration, the research has led to the validation of “green” techniques with low environmental impact, as alternatives to traditional toxic biocides. The most significant results concerned the combined use of UV-C irradiation and the application of essential oils. In particular, clove essential oil (*Syzygium aromaticum*), rich in eugenol, was selected for its excellent antimicrobial properties, enabling the removal of biological biofilms from opus tessellatum floors and frescoed walls without altering the original material. The interventions were complemented by consolidation and grouting work using mortars specially formulated to be reversible and compatible with the historic materials.

In addition to physical conservation, the project has invested heavily in digital innovation and social engagement through the “Baia Risonante” initiative. To ensure accessibility to a site that is often closed to the public or partially submerged, interactive 3D models and virtual tours have been created and uploaded to the Sketchfab platform, enriched with information hotspots detailing the findings of the investigations. A distinctive feature is the podcast “L’Eco di Baia”, produced in collaboration with Run Radio: this tool transforms technical restoration reports into

an immersive, multi-sensory narrative, using 3D-recorded ambient sounds from within the park to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and the general public.

Finally, the project has promoted citizen science models for participatory environmental monitoring. Due to limited network connectivity in the park, a low-cost system based on the Google suite was implemented, allowing visitors to manually record and upload the water level in the Temple of Mercury online. This collective contribution feeds into a dynamic dataset useful for monitoring the effects of bradyseism and raising community awareness of the vulnerability of the heritage site.

IV. Agrigento: Theatre (suburban area)

In Agrigento, work has focused on the monumental heart of ancient Akragas, particularly in the area of the theatre and the agora, through close collaboration between the University of Catania (UniCT, Gerogianni), the Polytechnic University of Bari and the Valley of the Temples Archaeological Park. The research has made it possible to reconstruct the urban topography of the ancient city, moving beyond a fragmented view consisting of isolated features.

One of the most significant findings was the definitive location of the monumental fountain and the ancient theatre, long considered a “topographical phantom”. The building, with a diameter of approximately 95 metres, stands as one of the largest performance complexes in Greek Sicily. From a technological perspective, Agrigento served as a testing ground for the Apple LiDAR sensor integrated into mobile devices, used for the rapid and accurate surveying of the findings uncovered during the excavation.

V. Baghdad, Iraq, Archaeological Park

The University of Catania (Laneri, Russo) has carried out restoration and consolidation work on the mudbrick structures in the area of the planned Baghdad Urban Park, in collaboration with the State Board of Antiquities and Heritage. The mudbrick walls were discovered during the archaeological excavation, using innovative restoration techniques. The following activities have been completed:

- Diagnostics and analysis of the state of conservation of the mudbrick during the excavation;
- Conservation interventions on exposed mudbrick architecture;
- Restoration work by Nearchos, carried out with a view to sustainability, using raw materials from decayed mudbricks available on site, as well as material from nearby sources, analysed by Claudio Prospero Porta. This was supplemented by preliminary diagnostic analyses carried out by the staff;
- Planning of the roofing for the archaeological structure by architect Carlo Pianossi.

VI. Turin: The King’s Apartment (Royal Museums of Turin) (Urban areas)

The University of Turin (UniTO) also coordinated an integrated environmental monitoring project at the King’s Apartment in the Royal Museums of Turin (Failla, Cutullè, Lo Giudice, Scalarone).

This project focused on establishing guidelines for the restoration of interior spaces through an in-depth conservation and analytical study of indoor environments.

The research, documented in the scientific paper entitled “Integrated environmental monitoring for heritage conservation: the case of the King’s Apartment in the Royal Palace of Turin”, adopted an integrated approach to predict the risks arising from climate change and inadequate spatial planning, extending the analysis to include the vulnerability of artefacts preserved in enclosed spaces. The research team drew on a range of specialist expertise to analyse how materials respond to environmental stresses.

In terms of output and dissemination, the project has yielded significant results:

- Scientific output: Three scientific publications and nine papers presented at international conferences have been produced.
- Digital dissemination: A 3D virtual tour of the apartment has been created, serving as a key tool for ensuring public access to and the documentation of the site’s condition.
- Training: The data and methodologies developed were incorporated into a specific learning object for the creation of the MOOC “Restoration Today: Theories and Methods”, aimed at transferring the technical knowledge acquired in the field of preventive conservation and microclimatic monitoring.

Together with the monitoring of the upper floors of the Casa della Caccia Antica in Pompeii, this study confirms UniTO’s strategy to implement advanced monitoring systems for the protection of heritage from natural and anthropogenic risks.

VII. Catania: Portico dell’Atleta (urban area)

The project on the so-called Portico dell’Atleta in Catania, led by the University of Catania (UniCT, Malfitana, Cerasa, Indelicato) in close collaboration with the Archaeological Park of Catania and the CNR, is an excellent example of a pilot project for the management and enhancement of “invisible” or “hidden” archaeological heritage within multi-layered urban fabric. Located in the Baroque heart of the city, beneath Via Crociferi and the Alessi staircase, the site documents a settlement sequence spanning from the Greek era to the Middle Ages, with a Roman Imperial-era (1st–2nd century AD) peristyle complex at its monumental core, enriched by fine mosaic floors, marble cladding and traces of wall frescoes.

Spoke 6 has launched a process of “active knowledge” aimed at transforming this forgotten site into a laboratory of innovation. Activities have focused on securing the premises to ensure accessibility and on developing advanced communication models.

One of the technological cornerstones of the project was integrated digital documentation: using laser scanning and differential GPS surveys, the researchers created a digital twin of the monument. This ultra-high-resolution model serves not only diagnostic purposes – to monitor the impact of humidity and vibrations – but also provided the basis for the creation of immersive virtual tours and a 3D reconstruction video. These tools allow the original appearance of the

portico and its dramatic niches to be visualised, overcoming the physical limitations of an underground visit.

A result of great scientific and symbolic significance was the recovery and reinstallation in situ of the marble torso of the athlete, an outstanding sculptural work from the 1st century AD that gives the complex its name. The statue, discovered in 1989 walled up in a room during a Byzantine-era renovation, has been the subject of new diagnostic studies to determine the origin of the marble and traces of polychromy.

VIII. Pantalica (SR) (extra-urban area)

The site of Pantalica, a UNESCO World Heritage Site since 2005, represents one of the most significant case studies for the application of the concept of “stratified landscape” or “palimpsest”. Located on a limestone plateau between the valleys of the Anapo and Calcinara rivers, the site bears witness to an almost uninterrupted human presence from the Late Bronze Age to the medieval period. The research conducted by the University of Catania (UniCT, Militello, D’Amico, Battiato, Arcidiacono, Barbagallo, Strano), in collaboration with the Archaeological Park of Syracuse, adopted a multidisciplinary approach structured along several lines of action that integrate the recovery of historical data with the most modern field investigation technologies.

a) The revision of Legacy Data and archival materials

A fundamental axis of the research was the recovery and systematic study of archival documentation, starting from the notebooks of Paolo Orsi preserved at the Regional Museum of Syracuse. The work of transcribing the notebooks (in particular nos. 27, 28, 36, 57, and 80) made it possible to reconstruct not only the first scientific discoveries made between 1889 and 1910, but also the working method of the archaeologist from Rovereto and his relationship of trust with local workers. At the same time, a critical revision was initiated of the materials from the excavations conducted by Luigi Bernabò Brea in the 1960s, many of which were stored in the museum warehouses in a summary manner or only partially published. This reorganization activity of about 55 boxes of materials led to exceptional discoveries, such as the reassembly of a cinerary amphora from the 8th century BC, the only example of this type so far known at Pantalica, which documents a phase of cultural transition of great significance.

b) New field investigations and systematic mapping

Field research activities focused on an area of about 20 hectares located on the summit plateau between the Anaktoron and the fortifications of Filiporto, an area historically neglected due to dense vegetation. A devastating fire in July 2023 paradoxically facilitated the start of an intensive and systematic survey, organized through a grid of 40×40 meter survey units. Preliminary results revealed a much more substantial occupation of the plateau than previously hypothesized, leading to the identification and geolocation of about 150 new hypogean structures and numerous standing wall alignments. These data contribute to redefining the urban layout of the

site, suggesting the existence of a dynamic and long-lasting settlement that goes beyond the traditional view of Pantalica as merely a necropolis.

c) Analysis of grinding tools and faunal remains

The study of movable materials found during surveys has offered new perspectives on the economic history of the site. The discovery of over 600 lithic grinding tools (querns and grinders), distributed across the entire plateau, indicates the presence of production activities and cereal processing rooted in the territory. The use of local basalts from the beds of surrounding rivers demonstrates a deep knowledge of natural resources. At the same time, the analysis of over 2,160 animal bone fragments from the Anaktoron area revealed a clear predominance of bovine remains (up to 89%), suggesting that the megalithic building may have been the site of communal consumption practices of high-value meat. These elements, together with the presence of casting molds and prestige vessels, reinforce the hypothesis of a centralized productive and food system linked to prehistoric political power.

d) Methodological innovation: the AR record

To manage the complexity of the collected data and overcome the gaps in national cataloguing standards, the project led to the development of new documentation tools. The AR record (Rock-cut Architecture) was created, specifically designed to analytically describe artificial cavities created by subtractive processes, integrating topographical, morphometric, and interpretative data.

e) Digitization and enhancement of rock-cut churches

The final phase of activities concerned the digital memory of the rock-cut Middle Ages of Pantalica, focusing on the churches of San Nicolicchio and the Crucifix. The use of the Matterport Pro3 system made it possible to produce very high-resolution 3D surveys integrating LiDAR geometry with RGB imaging. These “digital twins” are not simple visual models, but heuristic tools that allow precise analysis of the relationship between excavated architectures and the fragile surviving medieval painted decorations, often difficult to read or access. The iconographic study thus made it possible to confirm the early medieval chronology of the first nucleus of San Nicolicchio (9th century), linking it to the resumption of settlement in the area near the Anaktoron in the Byzantine period.

IX. Haghia Triada, Crete (extra-urban area)

The case study of Haghia Triada, in Crete, focused on the Royal Villa, a monumental multi-storey building from the Bronze Age (2nd millennium BC). The investigation was conducted by the University of Catania (UniCT, Puglisi, Chiricallo), in collaboration with Spoke 5 (D’Agostino). The main challenge in this context is represented by the fragmentary nature of the ruins and the need to virtually reconstruct missing portions, such as the upper floors, which constituted about half of the total volume of the building.

To overcome the arbitrariness of traditional reconstructions (often perceived as opaque “black boxes”), the project applied the Extended Matrix (EM) methodology. This approach makes it possible to transform the 3D model into a true three-dimensional archive, in which each

reconstructive hypothesis (Virtual Stratigraphic Unit) is directly connected to the metadata and paradata (archival sources, excavation notebooks from the last century, typological comparisons) that justify its existence.

The evolution of the research led to the creation of several versions of the model, from 1.0 to 3.1, the latter capable of restoring the real three-dimensional identity of the Villa with a covered surface of about 3500 m². The model made it possible to better understand the management of internal flows, distinguishing between ceremonial quarters with controlled access and service areas. In addition to its scientific value, the results were used for enhancement through immersive videos and a 3D prototype at a scale of 1:200, exhibited in Catania in 2023. The final objective remains the integration between EM and ArchaeoBIM in order to also verify the structural validity of the reconstructed Minoan architectures.

X. Villa of Realmonte (Agrigento)

UniCT (Malfitana, Cerasa, Indelicato, Cataldo) conducted and completed an articulated program of activities and investigations for the study and enhancement of the Roman Villa of Realmonte-Durruei. The site, an important *villa maritima* of the Roman imperial age, had been selected at the project stage as one of the test sites for the implementation of monitoring and conservation procedures in critical coastal contexts, characterized by strong erosion and degradation.

The team led by prof. Malfitana therefore worked on the construction of a scientific “knowledge plan” to overcome the fragmentary nature of previous excavations and to achieve a detailed understanding of the settlement and socio-productive dynamics of the complex. The technical and scientific activities included:

- *Archaeological excavations*: the three excavation campaigns (June 2024, December 2025 and September 2025) conducted at the Villa of Realmonte made it possible to update the archaeological framework through the deepening of diagnostic trenches placed in crucial points for understanding the context.
- *Geospatial analysis*: the geomorphological framework of the area was defined with greater precision (also through non-invasive investigations with ground-penetrating radar and close-range photogrammetry), and an integrated survey of the visible structures was carried out using high-precision topographic instruments. From the outset, the activities focused on the digital precision survey of structures and the geomorphological context. A Leica RTC360 laser scanner was used for the entire villa, supported by Total Station and DGPS, obtaining a high-density point cloud with millimetric accuracy.
- *Digital modeling*: the collected data were processed to produce updated GIS cartography, integrated into a geodatabase compliant with the scientific standards of the CHANGES Project. In addition, detailed plans and sections (scale 1:50) and a high-precision 3D model were derived from the point cloud. The latter, thanks to its chromatic and volumetric accuracy, serves as a basis for monitoring and predictive analysis of degradation phenomena. The systematic use of drones and close-range photogrammetry also made it

possible to generate a large digital dataset, from which orthophotos and terrain models were produced using Structure From Motion software.

- *Advanced monitoring*: between November and December 2025, a multimodal sensor network (RESEMM Project) for monitoring was installed with the support of the team. The monitoring system consists of a weather station for recording environmental, pollutant, and acoustic parameters, alongside two multispectral cameras and a thermal camera. These instruments make it possible to detect anomalies not visible to the naked eye, such as variations in humidity, salt deposits, infiltrations, and deep structural defects.
- *Research and dissemination*: during the course of the project, the team produced 8 scientific publications (6 of which focused on the Realmonte context), as well as a detailed virtual reconstruction of the Villa that synthesizes previous knowledge and the initial results achieved during the years of activity just completed.

Overall, the activities carried out made it possible to transform the Villa of Realmonte–Durruei into a reference case study for the integrated application of advanced methodologies of investigation, monitoring, and enhancement in coastal contexts. The results achieved constitute a solid basis for future strategies of protection and sustainable use of the site, fully in line with the objectives of the CHANGES Project.

4.4 Macro-scale: cities and territory

The macro-scale approach of the CHANGES Project (Spoke 6) marks a crucial methodological shift: attention moves from the single monument to the complexity of the territorial system, interpreting heritage as a “historical framework” inextricably linked to its environmental and anthropic context.

At the urban scale, activities focused on three case studies: the design interventions in the cities of Leonforte and Poggioreale in Sicily, the SIRIUS Project in Ravenna, and the Fountains and Monuments project in Turin.

I. Leonforte and Poggioreale antica: Design interventions

The research activity conducted by the University of Catania (UniCT, Carocci, Gallotta) on stratified urban landscapes has taken Sicily as a privileged laboratory for studying the dynamics of abandonment and the resilience strategies of historic centers. The interventions focused on two paradigmatic cases, Leonforte and Poggioreale antica, which, although starting from different histories (progressive depopulation for the former and a traumatic event for the latter), share the need for new methodologies of preventive conservation and sustainable enhancement.

- *Leonforte: the Granfonte district and the “decalogue” for rural dwelling*

In the Granfonte district of Leonforte, the oldest nucleus of the seventeenth-century foundation city, the research integrated historical archival investigation with the direct survey of “peasant houses.” The study of the documents of the Branciforti family made it possible to identify an endogenous hydrogeological vulnerability, linked to landslides and

historical floods (such as those documented in 1740 and 1809) that marked the fate of the district. These fragilities were aggravated over time by lack of maintenance and uncontrolled building transformations.

The operational core of the intervention is the definition of a decalogue of conservation interventions, aimed at safeguarding the identity of the rural building fabric. The proposals concern ten key aspects, from the ground connection (relationship between rock and masonry) to the system of vaults and roofs, up to the paving of public space. The objective is not only material restoration, but the creation of a model that makes these rural dwellings attractive again for contemporary living, while at the same time ensuring the safety of public routes through a feasibility study commissioned by the local administration.

- *Poggioreale antica: an open-air museum of “frozen” memory*

The case of Poggioreale antica, definitively abandoned after the Belice earthquake of 1968, represents for the researchers from Catania a paradigm of “frozen” ruination. Unlike other centers where the rubble has been removed or incorporated into artistic interventions, Poggioreale preserves an extraordinary urban readability that still allows the study of the ways of building and living in the 17th and 18th centuries.

The pilot project developed by the University of Catania proposes the transformation of the site into an “open-air museum.” The strategy is articulated in three sequential phases:

1. Safety measures (M1): minimal interventions to eliminate the risk of collapse of unstable parts along the main visitor routes, such as Corso Umberto I.
2. Consolidation (M2): repair and protection of the most significant structures, with particular attention to the characteristic stone and gypsum vaults typical of the place.
3. Restoration and memory (M3): interventions aimed at bringing out historical memory through informational installations and the use of some interior spaces, integrating material aspects (the ruins) and immaterial aspects (the history of the interrupted community).

This vision transforms the ruin from an abandoned “relic” into a stone archive, capable of narrating the evolution of the territory and reactivating the identity link with the community that today resides in Poggioreale nuova.

II. Turin: Project “Fountains and Monuments in the public space”

The project “Fountains and Monuments in the public space of the city of Turin”, conducted by the Fondazione 1563 within Spoke 6 of the CHANGES program, represents a pioneering initiative aimed at defining new models for the planned conservation of outdoor cultural heritage. The central objective is to overcome the logic of “emergency” restoration in favor of management based on coordinated, continuous, and data-supported maintenance, capable of ensuring the safeguarding of assets over time and efficient resource management.

The project was developed through a local micro-hub that brought together diverse competences: Fondazione 1563 handled the conception and management, making use of the technical-scientific consultancy of the Centro Conservazione e Restauro “La Venaria Reale”

(CCR) for restoration methodology aspects, the Fondazione LINKS for technological innovation, and Ithaca S.r.l. for geographic data management. This synergy was implemented in constant dialogue with the Municipality of Turin and the local Superintendence.

The methodology: the Protocol and the Case Studies

The methodological core of the intervention is the definition of an operational Protocol that systematically organizes survey activities, risk analysis, and intervention planning. To validate this methodology, five urban monuments were selected, heterogeneous in materials (stone, metals, concrete) and conservation state:

- The Monument–fountain of the Fréjus Tunnel in Piazza Statuto, taken as a pilot case for its extreme structural and material complexity.
- The Monument to Cavour in Piazza Carlo Emanuele II.
- The Monument to Angelo Brofferio in Corso Siccardi.
- The Fountain of Via Santa Chiara, chosen to document procedures following acts of vandalism.
- The Monument to the Italian Driver in Corso Unità d'Italia.

The analysis of these assets involved the use of advanced survey sheets, integrated with specific glossaries for the degradation of stone and metal materials, enriched by microclimatic and environmental data.

Technological innovation: the MAPPA platform

In support of the Protocol, the digital platform MAPPA (Platform for Agile and Planned Maintenance of Outdoor Cultural Heritage) was developed. It is a GIS–based geodatabase that centralizes all information into a single digital ecosystem, overcoming fragmentation between paper archives and scattered files. The main features of the platform include:

- Digital Twin: each monument is represented by an interactive and navigable 3D model that allows operators to precisely identify degraded elements during inspections.
- Immersive Monitoring: the integration of 360° views (virtual tours) allows examination of the environmental context of the asset.
- Predictive Management: the system is able to automatically calculate urgency levels of interventions by cross–referencing detected damage data, generating alerts and scheduled deadlines.

Results and Recognition

The project achieved significant institutional success by winning the CHANGES Awards at the beginning of 2025, a prize awarded for the platform’s ability to transform heritage protection from an emergency–based logic to a planning–based logic.

The Turin experience thus stands as a scalable and replicable model, not only for other Italian cities but also for different types of assets (including indoor ones), laying the groundwork for technological transfer that brings academic research toward concrete operational solutions for public administrations.

III. Ravenna: The SIRIUS Project

The SIRIUS Project, coordinated by Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna (UniBO, Vandini, Sara Fiorentino, Anna Casarotto, Ilenia Falbo, Alessandro Iannucci), constitutes one of the central initiatives of Spoke 6 within the CHANGES program, fully reflecting the partnership’s ambition to integrate humanities and scientific disciplines for heritage protection.

The intervention fits within the general objectives of the Spoke, aimed at developing multidisciplinary methodologies for the historical understanding and conservation of tangible cultural heritage. In particular, SIRIUS stands out for its macro-scale approach, a research dimension that goes beyond the analysis of the single monument to focus on the complex systemic relationships linking assets to their territorial and urban context.

The operational core of the research is represented by the historic urban context of the Arian Baptistery in Ravenna, taken as a case study for defining advanced protocols of risk assessment and preventive conservation. The activity of the Bologna research group aims to create scientific tools capable of anticipating degradation processes in complex urban environments. This model, based on the principles of Heritage Science, aims to define protection standards capable of mitigating the impact of environmental and anthropic pressures on large monumental complexes. A fundamental outcome of the activity is the development of a platform/database dedicated to the storage and management of data collected at the Ravenna site. This digital tool is not a simple collection of information, but an operational support aimed at implementing planned maintenance strategies, ensuring management of the asset that is both scientifically rigorous and sustainable in the long term.

IV. Ischia: the archaeology of an Island

The case study of Ischia (ancient Pithekoussai) constitutes an exemplary model of multidisciplinary research that intertwines archaeology, history, and geology. The island, the first Greek colony in the West, has been investigated through a synergy between the University of Milan (UniMI, Olcese), the École française de Rome, and private partners such as Istemi srl and Advice SRL, focusing on the conservation and enhancement of a heritage made vulnerable by the volcanic nature of the territory and by recent seismic (2017) and hydrogeological (2022) events. The approach was territorial, as well as multidisciplinary, focusing both on the global context and on individual case studies.

The territorial approach: Rock-cut wine presses and the wine landscape

The research also addressed the theme of rock-cut wine presses, imposing structures carved into the tuff of Mount Epomeo used for grape pressing. Through the use of gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) on the pores of the walls, biomarkers of alcoholic fermentation were identified, historically confirming the island’s winemaking vocation. The analyses revealed that archaic amphorae mainly contained white grapes, but also red wine and fermented beverages based on Rosaceae such as apples or pears. The digitization of these artifacts, often abandoned in the Bosco della Falanga or on Mount Corvo, aims at the creation of an open-air museum and sustainable wine tourism routes.

Digital methodologies and scientific results

Data integration was carried out through a Geographic Information System (GIS) based on QGIS, which organizes archaeological, topographic, and environmental information. The system includes historical orthophotos from the 1950s, LiDAR surveys, and attribute records for each site, allowing the reconstruction of settlement evolution from Prehistory to the Early Middle Ages.

The archaeological area of Santa Restituta (Lacco Ameno)

Research focused on the hypogean area beneath the Basilica of Santa Restituta, where investigations led to the identification of the ancient *kerameikos* (ceramic district) of Pithekoussai. Seven kilns for ceramic production were identified, dating between the 8th and 3rd centuries BC, as well as workshops for clay processing and settling basins. Since the site is currently closed to the public for safety reasons, the activity focused on advanced digitization: terrestrial laser scanning surveys and very high-resolution photogrammetry were carried out to create a virtual tour and immersive videos ensuring digital accessibility to the site.

The submerged site of Aenaria and Roman trade

Another significant scenario concerns the bay of Aenaria/Cartaromana, a Roman coastal district now submerged due to bradyseism. The systematic revision of metal finds recovered in the 1970s made it possible to carry out isotopic analyses (in collaboration with the Universities of Padua and Freiburg), which revealed that the raw material (lead and galena) originated from the Iberian Peninsula, specifically from the Cartagena–Murcia and Linares areas in Andalusia. This data confirms the central role of Ischia in imperial trade routes. Among the finds digitized in 3D, a *foculus* (brazier) stands out, used for the creation of a digital archive for protection and study.

The activity also included the material restoration of ceramics, amphorae, and terracotta reliefs at the Museum of Pitheculusae, using methodologies that ensure their stability and readability. Overall, the Ischia case study produced 9 scientific publications, 5 conference presentations, and multiple high-definition 3D models created with structured light scanners.

V. Etna Area: Seismic risk analysis

In the area around Mount Etna, including many centers with numerous churches and historical buildings, the DICAR group (Massimino) consolidated the methodological approach for integrating local seismic response analyses within a GIS environment, completing and operationalizing the NTC 2018 response spectra procedures through their integration into the MOPS layer. This enabled the definition of a computational workflow applied to the evaluation of building periods.

Additionally, the group developed a special mixture of well-graded gravel–rubber mixtures, to be used in the foundations of historical buildings to reduce seismic impact on structures. The mixture was applied in the bell tower of the Church of San Giovanni Evangelista in Bronte. FEM analyses applied to it confirmed that the adoption of well-graded gravel–rubber mixtures (wgGRM) systems significantly reduce spectral acceleration and, consequently, the seismic demand on the structure, while improving the understanding of soil–structure interaction within the broader soil–wgGRMs–structure system.

VI. South-eastern Sicily: The Risk Atlas

In south-eastern Sicily (including the provinces of Catania, Enna, Ragusa, and Syracuse), the University of Catania, with the DISUM departments (Militello, Platania, Puglisi, Gerogiannis) and DICAR (Nigrelli, Fischer), found the ideal laboratory to experiment with the evolution of the traditional “Risk Map” into a more dynamic and systemic Atlas of Risk of territorial and urban heritage. The core of this innovation lies in overcoming the view of the cultural asset as an isolated entity. While traditional mapping tended to “pin down” the monument to a specific location, the Atlas adopts a relational method that connects each element to the dynamics of the surrounding landscape. This change proved necessary following the verification of national data, which revealed significant gaps: in the four provinces examined, the integration of Landscape Plan data made it possible to identify over 4,100 assets, compared to about 3,000 previously recorded, recovering above all a vast category of isolated and extra-urban assets previously ignored.

The operational tool that makes this integrated management possible is the ARPAS geodatabase (Risk Analysis in the Stratified Landscape), developed by Advice SRL within the cascade funding calls. Developed on PostgreSQL technologies and accessible via WebGIS, ARPAS allows the superimposition of different information layers to analyse the vulnerability of assets with respect to natural risks (seismic, hydrogeological, volcanic, fires) and anthropic pressures (such as overtourism or the abandonment of inland areas). One of the most innovative features of ARPAS is its ability to manage diachronic stratification: the system allows queries by chronological phases, making it possible to reconstruct the evolution of the landscape over time and to model how exposure to risk has historically changed.

The final objective of the Atlas is not mere cataloguing, but the provision of immediate decision-support for heritage institutions. Through the use of relational matrices that cross-reference asset typology, geomorphological characteristics (such as position on ridges or slopes), regulatory framework, and land use, the tool makes it possible to calculate the “magnitude of risk.” This synthetic indicator helps define a real ranking of intervention priorities, transforming scientific knowledge into a strategy of preventive and planned conservation capable of mitigating damage before it becomes irreversible. This line of research, which has produced 3 scientific publications, represents a scalable and replicable model for the protection of Italian historical landscapes exposed to multi-risk scenarios.

4.5 Platforms

All the data acquired during the project have been stored in the Cloud and in a NAS at the Department of Informatics in Catania. However, in order to make data accessible, three platforms have been realized through the Cascade Calls.

4.5.1 Geodatabase

The geodatabase was developed by Advice SRL. The cartographic platform is a digital tool dedicated to the integrated reading of cultural heritage and its risk factors. It is based on a

specially designed geodatabase that allows the exploration of thematic maps and territorial data that relate archaeological assets, landscape, and geological context. In particular, a Risk Map of the Hyblean Mountains area and south-central Sicily has been developed, integrating useful information for monitoring the state of conservation and for risk prevention, offering an immediate and comprehensible overview. It also incorporates HBIM (Historic Building Information Modeling) models, that is, three-dimensional digital models of historical buildings that integrate geometric, historical, and material information, developed for some significant case studies, including the Roman villa of Realmonte and the Benedictine monastery in Catania.

4.5.2 Remote Monitoring Platform

As part of the cascading calls for proposals (UniSA and Modula), the RESEMM Project has established a multi-scale, multi-level monitoring framework through the development and deployment of a sensor network across five sites within Spoke 6 of the project. These sensors enable the characterisation of the behaviour of complex systems using BIM-based digital twin models. The monitoring networks developed have been connected via a user-friendly, cloud-based software platform, designed with different levels of access. The networks have been built using low-power LoRaWAN wireless technology and a web-based interface to ensure and simplify operational management, whilst allowing for high modularity, including the reconfiguration of individual nodes to meet future requirements.

4.5.3 Knowledge Sharing Platform

A knowledge-sharing platform has been created by ISTEMI SRL as part of the Cascade Calls. It is designed to facilitate the communication and dissemination of research findings. The platform consists of a web-based space for sharing materials, with a dedicated section for sharing project-related materials and the results achieved. This space hosts data, documentation, reports, articles and other relevant materials. ICR developed a software platform enabling a virtual tour of the Hypogeum of Saints Peter and Paul in Matera, conceived both as a repository and as a tool for the dissemination and sharing of knowledge acquired during the restoration process. The virtual tour is currently accessible to all visitors on-site via a dedicated digital device. These platforms have however been integrated with the platform realized by Fondazione CHANGES for the dissemination of the project.

4.6 Summary and overall evaluation

The overall analysis of the results of Spoke 6 highlights the success of an integrated and interdisciplinary model for the study and conservation of cultural heritage. Specifically, the following elements can be identified:

- *Strong integration between research and application:* the articulation of activities according to the multi-scale approach (micro, meso and macro scale) has made it possible to test methodologies in different contexts. At microscale, eco-sustainable materials and

standardized protocols for data archiving and management were developed. At mesoscale, diagnostic monitoring and HBIM models were applied to monuments and sites, as demonstrated by the activities in Pompeii, and multidisciplinary conservation models were tested in Baia. Finally, at macroscale, projects on risk assessment in urban contexts were carried out.

- *Development of innovative technological tools*: the project led to the development of digital platforms, databases, HBIM models, monitoring systems and GIS tools for the organization of territorial and environmental data. In addition, products for public engagement were developed, such as exhibitions, MOOCs, podcasts and virtual tours.
- *Capacity for transfer to the institutional and productive system*: a significant capacity for interaction with public institutions and the productive system was demonstrated. Collaboration with companies through cascade calls and specific projects such as ISMC and RETINA fostered the development of technological and remote monitoring solutions.
- *Extensive and continuous scientific production*: over 250 scientific publications were produced. More than 150 conference contributions were also generated. The series “CHANGES: Research of Spoke 6” and the special issue of the journal *Heritage* entitled “History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage” represented the main tools for collecting, systematizing and giving visibility to these results.

In conclusion, the activities of Spoke 6 demonstrate the ability to build an effective model of integrated research across disciplines, scales and actors, providing a solid basis for future developments in the Cultural Heritage sector.

5. Conclusions

5.1 FAIR Data and perspectives: the legacy of Spoke 6

The activities of Spoke 6 (History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage) conclude having fully achieved the ambitious objectives set by the CHANGES Project. More than a simple reporting of results, this report documents the transition towards a new paradigm of conservation, characterized by three fundamental pillars:

I. A consolidated methodological model

The multi-scale approach adopted – from molecular diagnostics to territorial planning – has demonstrated how fragmentation between disciplines can be overcome through integrated digital workflows. The effectiveness of tools such as the Extended Matrix for reconstructive transparency and ArchaeoBIM protocols establishes a new methodological standard for the management of complex archaeological sites, ensuring that every scientific hypothesis is traceable and verifiable over time.

II. Sustainability and Material Innovation (Green Transition)

In line with the European DNSH (Do Not Significant Harm) principle, Spoke 6 has validated concrete solutions for low environmental impact restoration. The development of alkali-activated materials (geopolymers) derived from industrial waste and the use of natural biocides (essential oils) represent not only laboratory successes, but solutions ready for the market and for large-scale application in institutional conservation contexts.

In the case of battuto di lapilli, rubble mixture and material for mudbrick walls restoration, the actions foresaw planning and synthesis of materials capable of reducing the environmental impact of the entire production process through the use of km0 raw materials and the recovery of secondary raw materials by involving the system in the circular economy, without using heat treatment and thus lowering CO₂ emissions.

III. Digitisation and Data Accessibility

The creation of Digital Twins and interoperable information systems (such as the PyArchInIt plugin and dedicated GIS systems) ensures the preservation of historical memory even for those assets defined as “invisible” or at high risk. The standardisation of cataloguing languages (AR and FR forms) fills a regulatory and operational gap, offering public administrations already-tested tools for the active management of storage facilities and submerged sites.

5.2 Towards the post-PNRR: future perspectives

The results obtained do not exhaust their function with the end of the funding, but constitute the basis for:

- *Strengthening protection policies:* predictive models and integrated environmental monitoring systems (applied in Pompeii and Turin) offer protocols ready to be adopted by Planned Maintenance Plans of national archaeological parks.
- *Continuous dissemination:* the series “CHANGES: Research of Spoke 6” will continue to represent a scientific reference point, ensuring that the knowledge produced remains an accessible public good.
- *Public-private synergy:* collaborations initiated with the productive system through cascade calls have opened new markets for companies in the Heritage sector, consolidating the role of cultural heritage as a driver of economic and social development for the country.

In conclusion, Spoke 6 delivers to the national research system a model of “active knowledge” capable of responding to the challenges of climate change and digital transformation, while ensuring the maximum protection of historical material and its widest social accessibility.

6. Data Summary

The activities of Spoke 6 have produced a broad, articulated and methodologically coherent set of scientific, technological and applied results, deriving from a plurality of projects developed in collaboration among academic partners, research bodies, heritage institutions and private actors.

Overall, the results highlight:

- numerous technical deliverables and methodological reports;
- Involvement of more than 15 SME, with a strong interaction between research and business community.
- development of digital platforms, databases, HBIM models and monitoring systems;
- creation of tools for dissemination and valorisation (exhibitions, MOOCs, podcasts, virtual tours, docufilm).

The results show a strong integration between research and application, with the development of innovative methodologies for documentation, diagnosis, restoration and management of cultural heritage.

The dissemination of results was ensured through a plurality of channels, including the series “CHANGES: Research of Spoke 6” and the special issue of the journal Heritage, which made it possible to systematize and enhance the contributions of the different partners, ensuring the project visibility at national and international level.

Scientific series and dissemination of results

The scientific results of Spoke 6 are demonstrated by

- over 250 scientific publications, many of which in international journals and in the special issue of Heritage;
- more than 150 conference contributions;

Moreover, the results of Spoke 6 are included within the series “CHANGES: Research of Spoke 6”, founded within the project with the aim of presenting in an accessible and systematic form the variety of activities carried out and the results achieved.

The series represents a tool of synthesis and communication addressed to a broad audience, complementing international scientific production and contributing to enhancing the integration between disciplines, approaches and application contexts.

In parallel, a central role in scientific dissemination was played by the special issue of the A-class journal Heritage, entitled “History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage”, which collected numerous contributions developed within Spoke 6. The special issue represented a moment of systematization of results, offering an organic view of the methodologies developed and the case studies addressed, and ensuring international visibility to the project activities.

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Annex 1: Data report

Range of intervention	Key Case Studies	Key Innovation / Methodology	Output (KPI)
<p>Microscale (Artifacts and Collections)</p>	<p>Catania, Monastero dei Benedettini (CT), Matera, Positano, Frosinone (pitture rupestri), Roma (murali), Spoletto, Deposito del Santo Chiodo Festòs (Creta)</p> <p>Bologna: Collezione osteologica Catania, Collezione Archivio di archeologica, Centuripe, Collezione di iscrizioni. Milano, Collezione focolari neanderthaliani</p>	<p>Experimentation with new restoration techniques: eco-sustainable geopolymers (DNSH), volatile binders (menthol), active deposition (TMA),</p> <p>Development of fire-resistant storage systems,</p> <p>Implementation of systems for the management of archaeological materials (PyArchInIt),</p> <p>Implementation of documentation formats: additional ICCR forms; Digitisation and experimentation with new scanning techniques.</p>	<p>Validation of 5 conservation procedures Restoration of 20 artefacts from Ischia Restoration of 6 underground paintings and 1 mural Restoration of the crucifix by Giovanni Teutonico Reorganisation of the Festòs stratigraphic museum (4,800 crates reorganised) Digitisation of 4 collections (3D models of artefacts, 4 image databases (approx. 20,000 images) 6 monographs 4 publications in A-list journals Over 50 articles in journals and books.</p>
<p>Mesoscale (Monuments and Sites)</p>	<p>Torino–Musei reali, Pompei (Domus di Arianna, Casa della Caccia), Baia, Terme Agrigento Teatro, Villa reale di Realmonte Pantalica, Ischia, Santa Restituta Haghia Triada, Villa</p>	<p>Implementation of protective systems: Metagenomics for biodeterioration, 'green' biocides,</p> <p>Implementation of mesoscale restoration measures: consolidation and restoration systems (columns); consolidation of underground areas (Catania).</p>	<p>Validation of interventions to halt deterioration 1 innovative product (lapilli) 5 restoration and monitoring projects on sites and buildings 8 monographs 6 articles in top-tier journals over 60 articles in journals and books</p>

Range of intervention	Key Case Studies	Key Innovation / Methodology	Output (KPI)
	Baghdad Parco, Catania-Portico dell'Atleta, Realmonte-Villa	Implementazione delle forme di documentazione: sistemi Extended Matrix (EM), Digital Twin, HBIM	27 publications (Pompeii), 12 (Baia), 26 (Pantalica, Agrigento, Haghia Triada), podcasts, virtual tours
Large-scale (Cities and the Region)	Torino Ravenna Ischia Poggioreale e Leonforte Area etnea Monti Iblei,	Implementation of documentation formats: GIS, geodatabases Integrated indoor/outdoor environmental monitoring; implementation of systems for assessing various types of risk (human-induced, natural: seismic, fire, water-related, etc.) and systems for visualising these. Involvement of public and private stakeholders.	1 product (rubber compound) 2 risk maps 2 restoration projects 1 restoration of the Frejus Fountain 2 public engagement projects (Guidelines for urban conservation) 4 monographs, 4 articles in Category A journals, 3 digital platforms and geodatabases, 5 monographs 4 articles in Category A journals More than 30 articles in journals and books.